

RESEARCH ARTICLE

**THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
ON STUDENT'S LEARNING PROCESS**

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Abstract:

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant impact on educational system, which is now offering new pathways to student centric learning process. This study explores the impact of AI on students' academic experiences which survey has been conducted around 250 students feedback and opinion through structured questionnaire and the response analyzed through percentage wise This research is limited to understanding the student perspective on AI in learning. This research also focused to understand about how students use the AI tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, personalized learning environments, and virtual assistants to enhance their learning process Through a survey-based analysis, this study also explores the student active involvement in using AI technologies in their learning process and their effectiveness compared to traditional teaching methods in simplifying and understanding difficult concepts. Presently the role of AI in improving comprehension, creativity, and critical thinking in student learning process Results of the study reveal that a majority of students per are beneficial from AI tools in simplifying complex concepts and personalizing learning paths. However, there is also some concerns related to the data privacy and the ethical uses. The findings suggest that while AI can become most powerful tool in upcoming education system as students are more relay on AI., but AI cannot replace the traditional education system as it does not involve human interaction.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Education, Data Privacy, Learning, Students.

Introduction:

Now a day's The artificial intelligence (AI) in education has revolutionize the learning experience for students. AI is providing collaborative learning environments in educational field, especially virtual

learning assistants can facilitate students in Personalized Learning and focusing on Intelligent Tutoring Systems, Data-Driven Insights for educational field projects, These AI tools reshaping the student's idea and thinking offering opportunities to students in research field. AI can foster learning experiences to individual students' needs. The integration of AI is into various online learning platforms catering the needs of students anywhere and anytime AI is transforming education in multiple impactful ways like Recommend tailored content, adjust difficulty levels in real-time, Answer student questions instantly, give step-by-step explanations, translate languages in real-time, enable voice-based learning, Provide writing assistance etc.

All these AI tools is benefited students in multiple ways, AI tools help streamline the Analysing trends in learner data, recommending which topics to include, expand, or simplify and Identify gaps in understanding any topics in educational sector, The opportunities in artificial intelligence (AI) for students is very broad, AI Powered assessments in learning are helping students in experiential learning and in improving the specific skills in the respective domain. fast advancement in artificial intelligence has dramatically impacted the education sector AI has entered the learning process like whether an individual has acquired information, skills, and competencies known as learning outcomes.AI also plays an active role in the progression of Creative learning education In AI AR/VR environments, and interactive simulations make learning more engaging for students which can grade tests and provide instant, personalized feedback for students automating administrative tasks, and providing students with innovative tools for academic success.

The Use of Artificial Intelligence in Education

In present days' artificial intelligence can provide personalized recommendations and can easily monitor student progress through integrated learning platforms Thus students can access relevant materials and resources according to their individual needs. AI is focused on Automated Administrative Tasks in the fields like grading, scheduling and report generation which will significantly reduce the workload on educators.

Administrators can now analyse the vast amounts of data which will be providing insights about the drive informed decisions and strategies. Additionally, AI is also breaking down education barriers which catering different needs and learning styles.AI ensures good learning environment with effective software's like Speech recognition software, Data and Learning Analytics. Intelligent Tutoring Systems Chabot's and Virtual Assistants etc. one of the promising functions of AI is to summarize existing materials and to generate with reinforcing lesson plans with stimulate image creation.

The advent of AI is also open the doors for critical thinking and ethical considerations in education system along with so many benefits AI is also having some Privacy and Security Concerns that is People are wary about what personal data is collected and how it is used Many are concerns about how carefully their data is stored and how protected it is from being leaked. Even though these dis advantages AI has made significant impact on student learning process by scrutinizing data to students according to their requirements

Literature Review:

According to Michael Spector, Jia-Bao Liu, Jing Yuan, Yan L This study provided a content analysis of studies aiming to disclose how artificial intelligence (AI) has been applied to the education sector and explore the potential research trends and challenges of AI in education

According to Preeti Singh, Amit Verma, Sanjna Vij, Jyotsana Thakur in this digital transformation era, businesses have access to a greater volume of data than ever on their customer's behaviors. One of the most significant difficulties associated with social media marketing is anticipating people's interests to provide them with relevant content.

According to Abdelghani Benayoune, Abebe Ejigu Alemu AI investigates student perceptions of AI across various academic aspects, such as module outlines, learning outcomes, curriculum design, instructional activities, assessments, and feedback mechanisms. It evaluates the impact of AI on students' learning experiences, critical thinking, self-assessment, cognitive development, and academic integrity.

According to Amr Adel, Ali Ahsan Claire Davison AI algorithms that may distort educational content and the inability of AI to replicate the emotional and interpersonal dynamics of traditional teacher–student interactions AI provides a balanced analysis of the opportunities and challenges of ChatGPT in education, emphasizing ethical considerations and offering strategic insights for the responsible integration of AI technologies.

According to Matthew N. O. Sadiku¹, Tolulope J. Ashaolu, and Abayomi Ajayi-Majebi Artificial intelligence (AI) is the cognitive science that deals with intelligent machines which are able to perform tasks heretofore only performed by human beings. It is mainly concerned with applying computers to tasks that require knowledge, perception, reasoning, understanding, and cognitive abilities.

Objectives of the Study

- To find out how AI impacted student learning process in education
- To analyse how students using AI in their present curriculum study
- Understanding AI's Influence on Academic Performance

Research Methodology:

Research Design

The study based on quantitative research approach by using a survey-based descriptive design to collect and analyse student perceptions and opinion regarding the use of AI in present learning system.

Data Collection Method

A structured questionnaire was used to gather data. The survey was administered to approximately 250 students to collect their feedback and opinions on AI tools in education and in present learning system.

Sampling Technique

the sampling method is it appears to be convenience sampling, focusing on students who are accessible and willing to participate.

Data Analysis

Responses were analysed using percentage analysis to interpret the frequency and trends in student responses and the Each question's results were presented and interpreted individually in the "Data Analysis and Interpretation" section.

Scope and Limitations

- The study is limited to students’ perspectives only.
- It does not explore the views of educators or analyze institutional data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1) Which of the following AI-powered tools have you used?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 50 % of students are using AI tutors for there education purpose

2) "Do you believe AI-based tools and technologies are being used effectively in your school/educational institution

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 65% of students are believed in AI-based tools and technologies which can be used in educational institution

3) How much time do you spend using AI-based educational tools per week?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 66% of students using AI tools less than 1hr in their day today life

4) How would you rate your proficiency in using AI technologies?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 55%of students are beginner in using AI technologies

5) Do you feel that AI is more effective than traditional teaching methods?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 70% of students are believed in AI-based tools are more effective than traditional teaching methods

6) What concerns do you have about the use of AI in education?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 45% of students are worried about using AI-based tools and technologies in educational institution because of data privacy & security concern

7) Do you think AI can help personalize learning experiences for students?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 65% of students are believed in AI-based tools which can provide personalized experiences

8) Do you find AI-based tools helpful in improving your understanding of difficult concepts?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 70% of students are believed in AI-based tools which can help in improving your understanding of difficult concepts

9) Do you think AI can enhance creativity and critical thinking skills in students?

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 53% of students are believed in AI-based tools which can help in enhancing creativity and critical thinking skills in students

10) How satisfied are you with the AI-based tools currently available for education

From the above analysis it has been concluded that 80% of students are satisfied with in AI-based tools in education system

Findings of the Study

1. Following findings can be observed from the study
2. Most of students are believed in using AI technologies in their learning methods
3. It also been observed that students using AI tools for critical thinking and for simplifying concepts in learning process
4. Most of the students believed in using AI powered tools in rather then depend on traditional teaching methods
5. It also been observed that most of the students are beginner iin using AI technologies
6. Personalized experiences in educational system can be more possible in using AI powered tools
7. It also been observed that AI had made significant impact on student leaning process in understanding difficult concepts

Conclusion:

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has made significant impact on the educational domain and transformed the learning experience for students. This study explores and reveals that AI tools are widely used by students for simplifying complex concepts, catering personalized learning experience for students, AI also emphasis on enhancing creativity and critical thinking among students, as now a days it is believed among students that AI-based tools as more effective than traditional teaching methods but concerns regarding human interaction in the classroom is always there for AI using teaching methods, it is also believed that data privacy is also major concern in using AI tools usage in education system . The findings of the study suggest that AI has great potential to then traditional education by focusing adaptive learning environments inside classrooms in the real-time academic support. However, AI has given new dimensions and directions to students in exploring new subject and research work in education field. We cannot ignore there is a increase in that percentage use of AI tools using among students has been significantly raised over in the last two to three years .AI now a days made students to adopt with personalized learning process in their respective education field.

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